

A P O L L O

D5.3: Final version of integrated and tested APOLLO platform

WP5 – Platform development

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Table of Contents

Executive summary.....	7
1 Finalizing the APOLLO platform.....	8
1.1 Development methodology	8
1.2 Co-creation meetings.....	8
1.3 User Experience	8
1.4 Integration.....	9
1.5 Testing.....	9
2 APOLLO Architecture	10
3 APOLLO platform.....	14
3.1 Consultants / Farmer’s organisations.....	14
3.2 Models.....	14
3.3 Notifications	15
3.4 Minor functionality or UI changes.....	15
4 Next Steps	17

Table of Figures

Figure 1: Data coming through the orchestrator and the sFTP connection	11
Figure 2: APOLLO information flow diagram in the Spatial layer	12
Figure 3: APOLLO business logic layer architecture	13

Table of Tables

Table 1 – Glossary.....	6
Table 2 – Component technologies.....	12
Table 3 – APOLLO business logic layer technologies	13

Glossary

Abbreviation/Acronym	Meaning
API	Application Programming Interface
CSS	Cascading Style Sheets
HTML	Hyper Text Markup Language
HTTP	Hypertext Transfer Protocol
MVP	Minimum Viable Product
REST	REpresentational State Transfer
UI	User Interface
UX	User Experience
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation

Table 1 – Glossary

Executive summary

This document aims at describing the implemented changes and updates regarding the accomplishments made in WP5, throughout the course of the work package. Furthermore, there is a description of the improved functionality of the **APOLLO** platform and the necessary changes that were put into effect, based on the received feedback by the pilots.

Chapter 1 describes the methodology followed by the development team in order to successfully integrate the proposed improvements with the existing system. Chapter 2 describes in detail the architecture of the **APOLLO** platform with any changes made by the development team in comparison with the previous version that emerged from the necessity to incorporate the received observations and remarks. Chapter 3 provides an insight to the adaptations that were made in regard to the **APOLLO** platform, after careful consideration of the feedback provided by the users of the MVP version of the platform.

The last chapter mentions the next steps that are planned for the **APOLLO** platform and the primary importance of incorporating the received feedback from the current and future users.

1 Finalizing the APOLLO platform

The main goal in the final stage of development of the APOLLO platform is to improve its functionality, while taking into consideration not only technical criteria, but more importantly the pilot users' feedback. During this process, the development team evaluated the issues that have emerged, as well as the comments and observations of the users and designed an appropriate action plan in order to produce the optimal result.

1.1 Development methodology

One of the first aspects that were considered is following a different development methodology for the final version of the **APOLLO** platform, one better suited to this stage of the overall process. So far, the development team followed an agile methodology (SCRUM¹) to develop the platform so that the pilot users, who represent the end users, would be involved in the process and generate feedback. In this stage all the feedback has been collected and analyzed, discussions have taken place, bugs have been detected and improvements have been decided, so all in all, the necessary information is fully gathered. Taking this fact into consideration, the team followed a Waterfall² model approach, a relatively linear methodology. In this case, the sprints were very clearly defined a priori, in a straightforward way, containing usually one piece of functionality. Each new sprint began after the last one ended successfully and made use of the functionalities implemented in all the previous sprints.

1.2 Co-creation meetings

The results of the co-creation meetings have been very encouraging, since representatives of the three **APOLLO** user categories (local farmers, agricultural consultants, and technicians operating at farmers and/or water users' associations), as well as **APOLLO** developers, came together and produced noteworthy feedback. Afterwards, in order to adapt to the pace and the needs of the development process, the co-creation meetings merged with the pilots. As a result, both the quantity and quality of the received feedback were enhanced, which subsequently affects greatly the development of the desired robust final platform that will be in tune with the needs of the end users.

1.3 User Experience

As it was already mentioned in the previous deliverable D5.2, user experience³ is one of the main points of focus and great care was taken, in order for the platform to be easy and efficient to use and esthetically nice. Since this aspect is of great significance, it was well-defined right from the start, but also specific steps were followed, in order to ensure that the feedback was received from the pilot users and that this feedback was utilized appropriately, so as to improve the user experience regarding the platform. In particular, every comment was taken into account, evaluated and then the team decided on what changes should be implemented in order to handle each request. Afterwards, those changes were registered in the issue tracking software that the development team uses, in

¹ [https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scrum_\(software_development\)](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Scrum_(software_development))

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Waterfall_model

³ https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/User_experience

order for them to be worked upon in the upcoming sprints. Once those issues were developed and deployed the team tested the usability with pilot users to verify the desired effect.

1.4 Integration

The integration of the various **APOLLO** subsystems and the connection to the respective sources to download and process the data needed for the agricultural models, was a point of concern during the early stages of designing and development. Several discussions took place but despite the extensive preparations made, the **APOLLO** platform when put in place it revealed additions in logic which were needed to further bulletproof a reliable process. More specifically, when the first version of the platform (the minimum viable platform – MVP) was released and setup to function experimentally for the pilots, the team invited additional farmers to join the platform. As the number of cases grew, the geographical distribution became larger and the **APOLLO** servers started becoming more and more busy slowing down the data download and processing stages. Due to that the development team decided to improve the synchronization process and established a signaling system between the processes. For example, one of the issues that emerged was that there were days that the weather forecast was not available when **APOLLO** looked for it, or it only returned partial information which **APOLLO** did not realize and it was trying to feed the model calculations with the -missing or corrupted - weather information. Achieving better signaling helped the orchestrator determine what actions were ready to begin or which ones should be re-executed, all of which resulted in having a more streamlined **APOLLO** that can be easier monitored by the system administrators.

1.5 Testing

For the development of the final version of the platform, several changes were requested small or big, either to solve bugs or change the offered functionality. The mechanisms developed in the previous stages of the project, that were used to validate the behavior of the application compared to the initial plan were also used at this intense development phase. The testing mechanisms ensured the team that the fixes were implemented properly, without disturbing other functionalities, and confirmed that the system was stable and the integration concrete after each and every build. Furthermore, since new components were introduced, it was deemed necessary to determine the appropriate testing mechanisms in order to validate their behavior and make sure that the **APOLLO** platform as a whole, will function securely and reliably under any circumstances.

2 APOLLO Architecture

The **APOLLO** architecture plan was followed and made more specific, as it was initially described in D5.1 and then modified in D5.2. Consequently, more changes were introduced in several parts of the architecture as indicatively described below:

- **Integration with the soil moisture processing chain**

During the implementation of the orchestrator, it became evident that the soil moisture service made more sense to be called on a per field request instead of a single call, that was initially thought to use to return all the parcels. In addition, the requests were enriched with per field soil-type variables which proved essential for the services to give more accurate soil moisture results. Those options for soil type were: Sand, Clay, Silt, and Organic Matter.

- **Meteo Tool integration**

Initially the plan was for the Meteo Tool to offer an API (“Meteo receiver service”) that would be used by the **APOLLO** platform for communication and exchange of data. Instead the team preferred to establish an sFTP⁴ connection **from** Meteo tool **to** the **APOLLO** system and “push” there the appropriate forecasts in CSV format. This change was introduced in order for **APOLLO** to keep an open door to other services similar to the Meteo tool, to push their data onto its servers. Furthermore, the team preferred to keep a data acquisition approach like the soil moisture handling which was also pushed in the sFTP folder.

In terms of actions sequence, once the Meteo tool finishes uploading forecast data to the sFTP folder, a “finish signal” is sent to the **APOLLO** orchestrator which then triggers the essential workflows and grab the data.

- **Importing Data into Rasdaman**

The initial plan was to use the WSCT⁵ import utility to import georeferenced data into Rasdaman Petascope. As described in D5.2, unfortunately this utility was not properly working when attempting to save over the network, so the team had exposed a second endpoint (sFTP connection) to collect and import partner’s data into rasdaman locally.

Afterwards however, further changes were implemented regarding the import of data into Rasdaman. The sFTP endpoint was not used in this capacity after all. Instead only the systems of Weather and Soil moisture utilize sFTP endpoints and the data from these systems is not stored in Rasdaman. Rasdaman is exploited only from UBFCE as an internal database, in order to import EO data and then calculate indexes such as the Biomass Index, LAI etc. In conclusion, Rasdaman is indirectly involved in the overall architecture and does not constitute a common storage place for all EO data.

⁴ Secure File Transfer Protocol, a network protocol used for secure file transfer

⁵ The WCS Transaction extension (WCS-T) defines a standard way of inserting, deleting and updating coverages via a set of web requests <http://rasdaman.org/wiki/WCSTGuide>

Figure 1: Data coming through the orchestrator and the sFTP connection

- **Updates to the Orchestrator's structure and data workflow in the Spatial layer**

The team changed slightly some of the Orchestrator steps like session creation in mongo db, splitting the geojson with all the parcels into per parcel geojsons in order to support outgoing requests to the soil moisture processing chain. An indicative operational workflow for the Orchestrator is:

Task 1) Create a session for the current day in mongodb.

Task 2) Download Parcels and meta data from the **APOLLO** API.

Task 3) Trigger the Soil moisture service (API) to request the Soil Moisture per parcel.

Task 4) Wait for finish/error signals from any of the subsystems (Soil moisture service, EO biophysical parameters and meteorological service, Meteo tool).

Task 5) Upon "finish" receipt from the soil moisture service: Migrate the TIFF files from sFTP to the Preprocessor.

Task 6) Upon "finish" receipt from the EO biophysical service: Migrate the TIFF files of Leaf Area Index, Biomass, NDVI and Chlorophyll index per parcel to the Preprocessor.

Task 7) Upon "finish" receipt from the Meteo Tool: Migrate the CSV files from sFTP to the Preprocessor.

Task 8) Prepare the inputs for the advisory models(preprocessor) and output them in TIFF format. Actions include resampling and file transfer.

Task 9) Calculate the advisory models and output them in TIFF files. Input to the models is coming from the preprocessor (TIFF files) and the Meteo CSV files from task 5.

Task 10) Transform the output from the models (postprocessor) so it can be fed a) Into PostGIS for statistical analysis b) to the Mapserver stack for visualization purposes.

The orchestrator was developed in NodeJS.

Figure 2 presents data flow from the **APOLLO** main sources (WP3, WP4) fed into the advisory models and pushed to MapServer.

Figure 2: APOLLO information flow diagram in the Spatial layer

The technologies used in the modules in the diagram above are presented in the table below:

Modules	Technology used
Soil moisture service	Python and node.js
Meteo Tool	Operation workflow runs with a Bash script calling code prepared in Fortran to handle the preprocessor, actual model work and post processor
Biomass, NDVI, Leaf Area index, Chlorophyll Index	Python
Pre-Processor	Python
Processor (models): 1. Tillage Scheduling 2. Irrigation Scheduling 3. Crop Growth Monitoring 4. Crop Yield Estimation	All models were developed in Python
Post-Processor	Python
Orchestrator	Node.js
Storage	File system and Rasdaman

Table 2 – Component technologies

- **Changes to the APOLLO business logic layer architecture**

The **APOLLO** business logic layer architecture was slightly changed. Initially the plan was to use Mapserver with Mapscript. However Mapscript was causing a big load on Mapserver and made it very slow in responses. The team examines several other configuration options and in the end decided to remove Mapserver/Mapscript with Mapnik, an open source toolkit for rendering maps, which could handle the required work without overloading the server. An indicative operational workflow for the information flow in between the **APOLLO** applications and the database is:

Task 1) User creates a request in the **APOLLO** web or mobile app.

Task 2) The web server (apache/nginx) receives the request and responds back with the requested page.

Task 3) User’s browser parses the page which contains also calls to the API and Mapnik as well as for files (images, javascript code, etc).

Task 4) Any calls to the API are executed in the PHP pages to apply the **APOLLO** business logic and/or retrieve the respective information from the database (postgis).

Task 5) Any calls to Mapnik (WMS) are executed in NodeJS to visualize data over a map. The main source that feeds the Mapnik service are the files that were produced from running the models in the “data preparation workflow”.

Figure 3: APOLLO business logic layer architecture

The technologies used in the modules in the diagram above are presented in the table below:

Modules	Technology used
APOLLO API	PHP using Laravel API
Database storage	PostGIS
File Storage	A common file storage based on linux
Map server	Mapnik
Web server	Apache/Nginx

Table 3 – APOLLO business logic layer technologies

3 APOLLO platform

After the MVP⁶ first version of the app was released and was successfully used by the pilot users, a large amount of feedback was collected concerning the functionalities of the **APOLLO** platform. This feedback was invaluable to the attempt to create a better **APOLLO** version that can fit the user needs. During the pilot period, the team changed and tested some of the already provided user interfaces to measure usability and the reevaluate the provided information either as part of existing user scenarios or upon new workflows established to better server user expectations. Following this process, the team worked more with UX experts to make the design of the application more easy to scale up to support more farms or more users. By examining the results of this process the team categorized the outcomes using two labels a) necessary and feasible improvements that were gradually incorporated and b) necessary improvements but not feasible within the logical limits of a project as **APOLLO**.

Indicative results from the described process are mentioned in the following sub-chapters.

3.1 Consultants / Farmer's organisations

As described in D5.2, aside from farmers, consultants and farmer's organizations were planned to be actors of the **APOLLO** platform and get similar services to that of the farmers. The implementation of this feature, was not prioritized to be included in the MVP version and instead, it was later created in parallel with the development of the user's part of the application. More specifically, once a consultant registers, they are able to add a new client (farmer) to the system and insert their respective parcels (farms) in the same way that a farmer adds his own parcels. The consultants can hav a summary view of all their clients' fields and they are able to select a specific farmer to view his/her fields and check if there are any new available service notifications.

3.2 Models

Another section of the platform that underwent changes was the models' implementation. Both the user's requirements and the feedback from the scientific team of the project, regarding the behavior of the models when applied specifically to different crop types in the various pilots, were taken into account in order to pinpoint the necessary adjustments. What is more, the development team itself proposed changes aiming to optimize the executed model workflows and bulletproof the proof against bad inputs, data unavailability or other not so typically frequent situations. The adjusted pseudocode for the models are listed in Annex I. Some changes that were discussed and implemented are the following:

⁶ Minimum Viable Product: A product that contains just about these features that are necessary for early users in order to provide feedback for the product.

- Added the ability of zoning a field into farm management zones. This is a typical example where the pilot users directly requested the addition of such a service, since in real life they have to manage parcels with different characteristics and they considered management zones a necessity. This service uses the NDVI from the crop growth monitoring service to produce results and the outcome is visualized over a map, that reflects the spatial variability of the crop in the field. Since the two services had many similarities, the development team grouped the results of the farm management service as an additional layer in the crop growth monitoring service. More details can be found on the pseudocode of the service in the annexes (Model: Zone Management Service Pseudocode).
- Recalculation of the service model results. During the initial development, the models were automatically executed daily at a predefined time, using inputs received either from the database or the weather service or even from data that were generated by other processes on the **APOLLO** server. This created a strong dependency for the models which needed to be executed at the specific day in order to benefit from the various available inputs. At some point, there was a need to add a new field in **APOLLO** and have all the historic time series data for the services available to the farmer, but unfortunately that was not feasible due to the way the process was designed and implemented. In order to amend that, the model classes were re-engineered, so that they can be completely independent of the application where they are being executed and they can be initiated with all the necessary parameters that will be needed for their execution without having to request additional information from other sources (i.e. database, weather service, etc). This resulted in a loosely coupled connection of the models and the **APOLLO** system, but also allowed the team to execute the models for any given time in the past and therefore allow for new parcels to enter the system and benefit from access to past information.

3.3 Notifications

One of the additions that was pending for implementation after the first version of the platform, was a more flexible notifications system which would go beyond the boundaries of the platform. Following the plan established from the user requirements, the users can now receive **APOLLO's** notification information outside of the application as well e.g. in their email and mobile phones. For this purpose, the following additions were included:

- Integration with the Nexmo⁷ SMS gateway in order to push alerts to users
- Enriched the user profile section with additional features that allow the user to have more control over notification options, such as whether to receive information by email or SMS, the optimal time to receive such information, etc.

3.4 Minor functionality or UI changes

After an initial pilot using of the **APOLLO** MVP version, users provided feedback concerning functionality issues and interface improvements that were categorized, prioritized and then gradually implemented. Indicative cases are mentioned below:

⁷ <https://www.nexmo.com/>

- Started using mapbox in order to improve the presentation of the basemaps and the user experience;
- User interface changes to the map control (leaflet.js) concerning layers and the legends but also the charts, in order to follow a more unified approach on a common color palette compatible with other similar applications;
- Fixes on bugs created by the rapid frequency of introduced platform updates and by the addition of new logic to the system, while trying to experiment with other options or delivering new user requests;
- Updated the data storage strategy concerning the caching of spatial information, so that large data time-series can be more easily and quickly served to the charts associated with the maps;
- Completion of the translation mechanism and inclusion of the translations;
- Additional user options, e.g. the user is now able to delete his/her account, to change his/her password, to set a profile photo and to set his/her language of choice;
- Additional features for the administrator e.g. create new users;
- Implementation of the “export layer” functionality for the **APOLLO** users;
- Implementation of the “reset password” functionality for the **APOLLO** users.

4 Next Steps

In the upgrade from the MVP first version to the final version of the **APOLLO** platform, the development team handled more than sufficiently all the issues that arose, as well as the introduction of new features and functionalities and the validation of the platform's performance. The result is a complete, stable, secure and reliable integrated system, specifically targeted to the end users, which is easy to learn and easy to use. The essential key in this accomplishment was without doubt the observations and comments of the pilot users in the form of valuable feedback, which in turn, when processed and exploited, elevated the platform to this high-end result. This is why, despite being more than satisfied with the final **APOLLO** platform, we plan to continue gathering feedback and taking into consideration the needs of the target users and to aim for improvements and enhancements that will render the final **APOLLO** platform excellent.

5 Annexes

Annex I: Models Pseudocodes

Model: Tillage Scheduling Service Pseudocode

This annex describes the steps needed to calculate the tillage scheduling in pseudocode format

Step1: Parameters and Data

- Import Crop Parameters (Crop Type, Sowing Date)
- Import Soil Data (Sand, Silt, Clay, Organic Matter)
- Import Weather Data (Yesterday Observations, 7-day Forecasts)
- Import Satellite Data (NDVI)
- Import Soil Moisture (Satellite or Yesterday Initial Soil Moisture)

Step2: Calculate Soil Hydraulic Properties

```
OrgC = OrgMat/1.724
BulkD = 1.510-0.113*OrgC
ThetaS = 0.838-0.283*BulkD+0.0013*Clay
ThetaR = 0.015+0.005*Clay+0.014*OrgC
Alpha = exp(-2.486+0.025*Sand-0.351*OrgC-2.617*BulkD-0.023*Clay)
NVG = exp(0.053-0.009*Sand-0.013*Clay+0.00015*(Sand)**2)
```

Step3: Define Soil Type

```
if ((Sand>=85) .and. ((Silt+1.5*Clay)<=15)) then
  SoilType="Sand"
else if ((Sand>=70) .and. (Sand<=91) .and. ((Silt+2*Clay)<=30)) then
  SoilType="Loamy Sand"
else
  if ((7<=Clay) .and. (Clay<=20) .and. (Sand>52) .and. ((Silt+2*Clay)>=30)) .or. ((Clay<7)
  .and. (Silt<50) .and. (Sand>43)) then
    SoilType="Sandy Loam"
  else if ((7<=Clay) .and. (Clay<=27) .and. (28<=Silt) .and. (Silt<=50) .and. (Sand<52))
  then
    SoilType="Loam"
  else if ((Silt>=80) .and. (Clay<12)) then
    SoilType="Silt"
  else
    if ((Silt>=50) .and. (12<=Clay) .and. (Clay<=27)) .or. ((80>Silt) .and. (Silt=>50) .and. (
    Clay<12)) then
      SoilType="Silt Loam"
    else if ((20<=Clay) .and. (Clay<=35) .and. (Sand>=45) .and. (Silt<28)) then
      SoilType="Sandy Clay Loam"
    else if ((27<=Clay) .and. (Clay<=40) .and. (20<=Sand) .and. (Sand<=45)) then
      SoilType="Clay Loam"
    else if ((27<=Clay) .and. (Clay<=40) .and. (Sand<20)) then
      SoilType="Silty Clay Loam"
    else if ((Sand>=45) .and. (Clay>=35)) then
```



```

SoilType="Sandy Clay"
else if ((Clay>=40).and.(Silt>=40)) then
  SoilType="Silty Clay"
else if ((Clay>=40).and.(Sand<45).and.(Silt<40)) then
  SoilType="Clay"
else
  SoilType="Error"
end if

```

Step4: Calculate Soil Water Parameters

```

PWP=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*15000)**NVG))

select case(SoilType)
  case("Sand")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*100)**NVG))
  case("Loamy Sand")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*100)**NVG))
  case("Sandy Loam")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*100)**NVG))
  case("Loam")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
  case("Silt Loam")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
  case("Silt")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
  case("Sandy Clay Loam")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
  case("Clay Loam")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*500)**NVG))
  case("Silty Clay Loam")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
  case("Sandy Clay")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*500)**NVG))
  case("Silty Clay")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*500)**NVG))
  case("Clay")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*500)**NVG))
end select

```

Step5: Calculate Crop Coefficient

```

Kcb = 1.5625 * NDVI - 0.1
fc = 1.318 * NDVI - 0.1877
Ke = 0.25 * (1 -fc)
Kc = Kcb + Ke

```

Step6: Initialize Model

```

if (Satellite_Soil_Moisture = True) then
  Soil_Moisture(0) = Satellite_Soil_Moisture
else
  Soil_Moisture(0) = (Yesterday_Soil_Water(0) -Kc* Observed_Evapotranspiration
+ Observed_Precipitation)/30

end if

Soil_Water = Soil_Moisture(0) * 30

```



```
Crop_Evapotranspiration(0) = Forecast_Evapotranspiration(0) * Kc
```

Step7: Calculate Soil Water Budget and Apply Tillage Rules

```
do i=1,6

  Crop_Evapotranspiration(i) = Forecast_Evapotranspiration(i) * Kc

  Soil_Water(i) = Soil_Water(i-1) - Crop_Evapotranspiration(i-1) +
Precipitation(i-1)

  Gravimetric_Soil_Moisture(i) = (Soil_Water/30)/BulkD

select case(SoilType)
  case("Sand")
    $LTL = 0.077;
    $UTL = 0.174;
    $WOPT = 0.140;
    break;
  case 'loamy sand' :
    $LTL = 0.106;
    $UTL = 0.188;
    $WOPT = 0.155;
    break;
  case 'sandy loam' :
    $LTL = 0.140;
    $UTL = 0.209;
    $WOPT = 0.177;
    break;
  case 'loam' :
    $LTL = 0.169;
    $UTL = 0.231;
    $WOPT = 0.199;
    break;
  case 'silt loam' :
    $LTL = 0.154;
    $UTL = 0.220;
    $WOPT = 0.188;
    break;
  case 'silt' :
    $LTL = 0.111;
    $UTL = 0.192;
    $WOPT = 0.159;
    break;
  case 'sandy clay loam' :
    $LTL = 0.194;
    $UTL = 0.252;
    $WOPT = 0.221;
    break;
  case 'clay loam' :
    $LTL = 0.228;
    $UTL = 0.280;
    $WOPT = 0.251;
    break;
  case 'silty clay loam' :
    $LTL = 0.227;
    $UTL = 0.286;
    $WOPT = 0.250;
```



```

        break;
    case 'sandy clay' :
        $LTL = 0.230;
        $UTL = 0.287;
        $WOPT = 0.256;
        break;
    case 'silty clay' :
        $LTL = 0.266;
        $UTL = 0.317;
        $WOPT = 0.287;
        break;
    case 'clay' :
        $LTL = 0.291;
        $UTL = 0.347;
        $WOPT = 0.314;
        break;
end select

if (LTL <= Gravimetric_Soil_Moisture(i) < LTL + 1/3*(Wopt-LTL)) then
    Tillage(i) = Orange
else if ( LTL + 1/3*(Wopt-LTL) <= Gravimetric_Soil_Moisture(i) < LTL + 2/3*(Wopt-LTL) ) then
    Tillage(i) = Yellow
else if (LTL + 2/3*(Wopt-LTL) <= Gravimetric_Soil_Moisture(i) < Wopt) then
    Tillage(i) = Green
else if (UTL >= Gravimetric_Soil_Moisture(i) > UTL - 1/3*(Wopt-LTL)) then
    Tillage(i) = Orange
else if ( UTL - 1/3*(UTL-Wopt) >= Gravimetric_Soil_Moisture(i) > UTL - 2/3*(UTL-Wopt) ) then
    Tillage(i) = Yellow
else if (UTL - 2/3*(UTL-Wopt) >= Gravimetric_Soil_Moisture(i) > Wopt) then
    Tillage(i) = Green
end do

```

Step8: Print Results

```

do i = 0,6

    write(Tillage.tif) Tillage (i)

end do

```

Model: Irrigation Scheduling Service Pseudocode

This annex describes the steps needed to calculate the irrigation scheduling in pseudocode format

Step1: Parameters and Data

- Import Crop Parameters (Crop Type, Sowing Date)
- Import Irrigation (True .or. False)
- Import Soil Data (Sand, Silt, Clay, Organic Matter)
- Import Weather Data (Yesterday Observations, 7-day Forecasts)

Import Satellite Data (NDVI)

Import Soil Moisture (Satellite or Yesterday Initial Soil Moisture)

Step2: Calculate Soil Hydraulic Properties

```
OrgC = OrgMat/1.724
BulkD = 1.510-0.113*OrgC
ThetaS = 0.838-0.283*BulkD+0.0013*Clay
ThetaR = 0.015+0.005*Clay+0.014*OrgC
Alpha = exp(-2.486+0.025*Sand-0.351*OrgC-2.617*BulkD-0.023*Clay)
NVG = exp(0.053-0.009*Sand-0.013*Clay+0.00015*(Sand)**2)
```

Step3: Define Soil Type

```
if((Sand>=85).and.((Silt+1.5*Clay)<=15)) then
  SoilType="Sand"
else if((Sand>=70).and.(Sand<=91).and.((Silt+2*Clay)<=30)) then
  SoilType="Loamy Sand"
else
  if((7<=Clay).and.(Clay<=20).and.(Sand>52).and.((Silt+2*Clay)>=30)).or.((Clay<7)
  .and.(Silt<50).and.(Sand>43)) then
    SoilType="Sandy Loam"
  else if((7<=Clay).and.(Clay<=27).and.(28<=Silt).and.(Silt<=50).and.(Sand<52))
  then
    SoilType="Loam"
  else if((Silt>=80).and.(Clay<12)) then
    SoilType="Silt"
  else
    if((Silt>=50).and.(12<=Clay).and.(Clay<=27)).or.((80>Silt).and.(Sand>=50).and.(
    Clay<12)) then
      SoilType="Silt Loam"
    else if((20<=Clay).and.(Clay<=35).and.(Sand>=45).and.(Silt<28)) then
      SoilType="Sandy Clay Loam"
    else if((27<=Clay).and.(Clay<=40).and.(20<=Sand).and.(Sand<=45)) then
      SoilType="Clay Loam"
    else if((27<=Clay).and.(Clay<=40).and.(Sand<20)) then
      SoilType="Silty Clay Loam"
    else if((Sand>=45).and.(Clay>=35)) then
      SoilType="Sandy Clay"
    else if((Clay>=40).and.(Silt>=40)) then
      SoilType="Silty Clay"
    else if((Clay>=40).and.(Sand<45).and.(Silt<40)) then
      SoilType="Clay"
    else
      SoilType="Error"
  end if
```

Step4: Calculate Soil Water Parameters

```
PWP=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*15000)**NVG))
select case(SoilType)
  case("Sand")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*100)**NVG))
  case("Loamy Sand")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*100)**NVG))
  case("Sandy Loam")
    FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*100)**NVG))
```



```

case("Loam")
  FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
case("Silt Loam")
  FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
case("Silt")
  FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
case("Sandy Clay Loam")
  FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
case("Clay Loam")
  FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*500)**NVG))
case("Silty Clay Loam")
  FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*330)**NVG))
case("Sandy Clay")
  FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*500)**NVG))
case("Silty Clay")
  FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*500)**NVG))
case("Clay")
  FC=ThetaR+((ThetaS-ThetaR)/(1+(Alpha*500)**NVG))
end select

```

Step5: Calculate Crop Coefficient

```

Kb = 1.5625 * NDVI - 0.1
fc = 1.318 * NDVI - 0.1877
Ke = 0.25 * (1 -fc)
Kc = Kcb + Ke

```

Step6: Initialize Model

```

if (Satellite_Soil_Moisture = True) then
  Soil_Moisture(0) = Satellite_Soil_Moisture
else
  if (Farmer_Irrigation = True) then
    Soil_Moisture(0) = FC
  else
    Soil_Moisture(0) = (Yesterday_Soil_Water(0) -Kc* Observed_Evapotranspiration
+ Observed_Precipitation)/Yesterday_Root_Depth
  end if
end if

Root_Depth(0) = Root_Max/(1+Root_C1*exp(-Root_C2*(days_from_sowing-Time_Max)))

Soil_Water = Soil_Moisture(0) * Root_Depth(0)
Crop_Evapotranspiration(0) = Forecast_Evapotranspiration(0) * Kc

```

Step7: Calculate Soil Water Budget

```

do i=1,6

  Root_Depth(i) = Root_Max/(1+Root_C1*exp(-Root_C2*(days_from_sowing-
Time_Max)))

  Crop_Evapotranspiration(i) = Forecast_Evapotranspiration(i) * Kc

  Soil_Water_PWP = PWP * Root_Depth(i)

  Soil_Water_FC = FC * Root_Depth(i)

```



```

Soil_Water_LAM = Soil_Water_FC - F * (Soil_Water_FC-Soil_Water_PWP)

Soil_Water(i) = Soil_Water(i-1) - Crop_Evapotranspiration(i-1) +
Precipitation(i-1)

if(Soil_Water(i) < Soil_Water_LAM) then
  Irrigation(i) = 1
  Irrigation_Dose(i) = Soil_Water_FC - Soil_Water(i)
else
  Irrigation = 0
end if

Soil_Moisture(i) = Soil_Water(i)/Root_Depth(i)

end do

```

Step8: Print Results

```

do i = 0,6

write(Soil_Moisture.tif) Soil_Moisture(i)
write(Crop_Evapotranspiration.tif) Crop_Evapotranspiration(i)
write(Irrigation.tif) Irrigation(i)
write(Irrigation_Dose.tif) Irrigation_Dose(i)

end do

```

Model: Zone Management Service Pseudocode

The calculation of management zones is further described in the following steps:

Step1: Transfer the NDVI time series for the selected field in a 3D array

Step2: Remove all pixels with NaN values that are <0 and >1

Step3: Calculate the average value of the time series for each pixel

Step4: Calculate the total average value of all the pixel averages

Step5: If the average pixel value is greater than the total average, then this pixel is stored using the label "High" and is assigned the color green, otherwise it is associated with the label "Low" and is assigned the red color.

Step6: Data can be visualized over a map

END OF DOCUMENT

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